

MODERN METHODS AND FACTORS OF IMPROVING SPEECH SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the methods and factors of improving speech activity of teachers. The proposed principles, methods, techniques and teaching tools are aimed at increasing the speech activity of teachers, preventing and eliminating dialect errors in the speech of school teachers.

Pedagogical speech, first of all, should ensure effective listening of students in class. The student who perceives the topic with the teacher's speech performs many different operations: concretizes sound information in visual images, connects it with existing knowledge, experiences, understands, remembers, follows the logic of the teacher's presentation, his develops thoughts. This is a difficult task for the listener, which should be taken into account when thinking through the content, pace, rhythm, logic, and convenience of the speech.

Speech in school classes showed that when the teacher violates the optimal speed of speech, students experience a sharp incompleteness and inaccuracy of perceived information, the amount of repeated incorrect information increases.

It is possible to show several modern methods of improving the methodology of formation of speech skills of teachers. These are:

1) development of self-control and speech culture, formation of an attitude towards mastering correct, literary speech in all situations of oral communication:

- education of the need to learn speech culture;

- it is important to pay special attention to the correctness of speech (compliance with language standards - accent, pronunciation, word formation) and purity of speech.

Working with dictionaries helps a lot in this: explanation, difficulties in combining words. Turning to them in difficulty enriches the speech.

In this place, weaknesses in speech (richness of speech, clarity, consistency, purity) are considered and attention is focused on working on their change.

2) development of self-control and expressive speech skills.

In this, attention is paid to intonation, relevance to the content, the use of figurative tools (epithets, metaphors), clarity of verbal imagery (excerpts from

works of art, aphorisms) and presentations are prepared.

When preparing the presentation, attention is paid to the following:

- what thoughts should be evoked;
- what mood needs to be created;
- intonation and rhythm during performance.

3) development of communicative abilities, social relations in the field of self-control and communication.

The condition of effective communicative behavior is the teacher's individual communication style. It is important to study social status in communication.

That is:

- attitude to people;
- communication process;
- mood management;
- understanding of people;
- ability to attract

The success of communicative behavior implies the development of a number of special abilities and skills in the teacher:

- socio-perceptive (the ability to act in a partner, to understand his inner state);
- the ability of social imagination (putting yourself in another's place, predicting the reaction);
- self-control in communication, ability to control mental state;
- the ability to voluntarily influence and offer.

4) development of general psychophysical personal characteristics that create the necessary conditions for successful acquisition of speech skills and abilities.

- development of imagination (recreational and creative);
- associative and figurative memory, fantasy.

A necessary condition for the expressiveness of the teacher's speech is his

mental view of the objects, events, and processes he talks about.

In this case, the speech becomes emotional, lively, we draw pictures with the help of language. Such speech cannot be achieved by willpower. It is necessary to develop the ability to see and hear the world in colors and sounds, pictures, and to learn to convey thoughts in words.

A teacher's speech is an improvisation in the true sense of the word, an unprepared speech that occurs during direct communication with students, when circumstances require an immediate reaction from the teacher. And he answers - a detailed answer, a story, a guide. In such situations, the responsibility of the teacher for the choice of words, forms of speech and the chosen tone of speech increases.

It is in speech behavior that the general culture and pedagogical culture of the teacher, the moral experience of his behavior, and his relations with students are manifested.

Based on this, it is necessary to improve the methodology of formation of speech skills in teachers, based on their speech activity, to look for activity from students as an example, to develop their speech using modern methods and factors. There are three levels of this:

1. Reproductive activity of schoolchildren is the lowest level of independent thinking (working according to a model, in which students apply the knowledge and skills they have acquired in a similar situation).

2. Partial research work - a high level of independence of thinking (for example, when writing free dictation, when it is necessary to retell the text, it is manifested in showing some independence in choosing the content and means of expression).

3. Search activity - the highest level of independence of thinking (for example, it is done when writing an essay).

Based on these levels, I. Ya. Lerner offers the following classification of methods of improving the methodology of formation of speech skills in teachers:

- explanatory and illustrative method: they perceive, understand, remember what the teacher said;

- reproductive method: work is done by students according to the model given by the teacher;

- problem presentation: students are taught to analyze events independently, the teacher formulates a problem and reveals evidence-based solutions and methods of orientation in a new situation;

- partial-search method: a problem is set and by asking questions, the teacher involves students in the process of solving it based on evidence, helps them find answers to their questions, keywords are formed by the teacher and given to students.

- research method: students work in parallel with the teacher, acquire new knowledge and ways of obtaining it, solve the problem as a result of analyzing the material, justify the conclusion.

The classification of methods of teaching speech activity, based on the levels of independent thinking, from sample work to partial research and full research, is a system of improving students' speech activity, and includes the following methods:

- 1) teaching to analyze texts;
- 2) teaching to choose language tools according to a ready-made sample in connection with the change of texts;
- 3) teaching creative use of language tools in connection with text creation.

Methods of using the first method: warning, explanation, selective dictation, comment writing, analysis of phonetic, grammatical, spelling and punctuation marks, making models of these expressions, leaving punctuation marks in the text without marking, etc.

The methods of using the second method are restructured sentences for the purpose of mastering syntactic constructions and putting punctuation marks, replacing some syntactic constructions with others, replacing some words, phrases with others, etc.

The methods of using the third (creative) method include free dictation, presentation, writing an essay, preparing a review of a literary work, a performance, writing an article in a newspaper, an abstract, theses, a synopsis, etc.

Of course, the principles determine the content and methodology of teaching. Based on the teacher, there are the following principles with this order of the methodological system of the development of the student's speech activity:

1. General didactic: systematic, scientific, existing, educational nature of education;
2. Special: communication, taking into account the native language of students, the complexity, functional approach helps to implement the example of the teacher's speech.

Thus, the principle of consistency determines that students' knowledge, skills and competences are formed systematically, that is, in a certain order and sequence: the logical connection of each element of the educational material with others, the teacher and prepares the student to master new material, with the next one building on the previous one. This didactic principle is based on a strict

adherence to the educational sequence and a logically consistent approach to education.

A teacher should work hard to form his pedagogical speech culture.

Rules of speech culture of the teacher.

1. The teacher should speak quietly, but in such a way that everyone can hear him, so that the listening process does not cause significant stress for students.
2. The teacher should speak clearly.
3. The teacher should speak at a speed of about 120 words per minute.
4. It is important to be able to use pauses to achieve an expressive sound - logically and psychologically. Speech without logical pauses is illiterate, without psychological pauses colorless.
5. The teacher should speak with intonation, i.e. be able to put logical accents, highlight individual words that are important for the content of the spoken sentence.
6. The tone gives an individual color to the teacher's voice and can significantly affect

the emotional state of students: it inspires, attracts, soothes.

The characteristics of the teacher's inner world, culture and spiritual wealth, confidence in the correctness of his words are the most important for the art of speech. S. L. Soloveitchik wrote: "Nowadays there is a lot of talk about the need to check the technical skills of the teacher, his voice, gesture, intonation. But more importantly, the teacher's moral character, communication style and behavior are the main is in line".

So, teacher speech culture is a capacious and multifaceted concept. Language elements specially selected and used in a particular communication are, in fact, speech. The correctness of such a choice depends on the knowledge of the author of the speech, his ability to consciously choose and use the necessary language tools during communication.